

Thematic grouping

Resource constraints challenges		
Challenge Group	Description	Source Papers
Computational and Memory Limitations	Fundamental computational and memory restrictions on cognitive cities devices such as IoT and sensors which hinders the implementation of robust security mechanisms.	P1, p3, p4, p5, p7, p8, p9, p12, P14, p16, P18, P19, p22, P23, P24, P28, p29, p30, p31, p36, p37, P38, p42, P43, P45, p46, P49, p50, p52, p56, p59, p60, p61, p62, p63, p64, p65, p69, p72, p75, p76, p77, p78, p81, p82, p84, p85, p86
Energy and Power Constraints	Battery and power limitations affecting security feature implementation and operational longevity.	p7, p8, p16, p18, p22 P23, P24, p29, p31, p37, p42, p45, p46, p50, p52, p56, p58, p61, p62, p65, p70, p72, p75, p76, p80, p82, p85, p86, GL3, GL8, GL11, GL20
Communication Constraints	Network and bandwidth limitations affecting secure data exchange.	P1, P12, P14, P22, P23, P24, P28, p29, p31, P34, p37, P42 p43, p50, p58, P76, p68, p80, p82, P83, p84, p85, GL2, GL11, GL24
System Complexity & Integration Challenges		
Challenge Group	Description	Source Papers
Heterogeneity and Standardization Gaps	Challenges from diverse devices, protocols, and platforms operating without unified standards.	p5, P6, p8, P19, p30, P35, P38, p40, p41, p43, p48, p50, p51, p54, p56, p59, p62, p63, p65, p69, P71, p72, p73, p76, p80, p82, GL2, GL3, GL15, GL16, GL23, GL25, GL26, GL29
Legacy System Integration	Difficulties incorporating outdated systems and technologies.	p36, p39, p41, p48, p56, P57, GL1, GL3, GL4, GL5, GL6, GL7, GL11, GL12, GL14, GL15, GL16, GL17, GL21, GL25, GL26, GL29
Scalability Management	Challenges managing the vast number of devices and complex interconnections.	P10, P13 p20, p36, p40, p42, p47, p48, p50 p51, p53, p59, p65, p69, P75, P80, GL2, GL3, GL6, GL14, GL15, GL16, GL17, GL20, GL21, GL24 ,GL25, GL26, GL27
Increased Attack Surface	Expanded vulnerability landscape created by interconnected systems.	p36, p61, p64, p69, p74, p78, GL1, GL2, GL3, , GL14, GL15, GL16, GL17, GL21, GL25, GL26, GL27, GL29

Security Design and Implementation Challenges

Challenge Group	Description	Source Papers
Security as an Afterthought	Neglecting security considerations during initial design phases.	P6, p12, p22, p25, p48, p53, p54, p55, p60, p66, p72, p74, p84, GL2, GL3, GL7, GL9, GL12, GL14, GL16, GL17, GL25, GL29
Update and Maintenance Issues	Difficulties maintaining security throughout device lifecycle.	P10, P22, p23, p30, p40, p48, p50, p64, p66, p69, p75, P76, P79, p80, GL3, GL4, GL11, GL12, GL15, GL28
Authentication and Access Control Weaknesses	Inadequate mechanisms for verifying identity and controlling system access.	P1, p8, p22, p29, p31, P32, p60, p62, p64, P71, p75, p80, GL3, GL8, GL12, GL13, GL18

Data Management & Advanced technology challenges

Challenge Group	Description	Source Papers
Data Privacy and Protection	Challenges protecting sensitive personal information collected in smart environments.	p7, p8, p13, P15, P20, P21, p26, P32, p33, P35, p39, p40, p43, p48, p53, p54, p55, p62, p64, p66, P71, p72, P83, GL2, GL6, GL10, GL11, GL14, GL15, GL17, GL20, GL21, GL23, GL24, GL26
Data Volume and Processing	Challenges related to massive data generation and management requirements.	P24, p29, p39, P49, p59, p61, p62, p68, p69, p72, p75, p80, p85, p86, GL2, GL3, GL14, GL18, GL20, GL21, GL24
Data Governance and Ownership	Challenges related to establishing and maintaining formal accountability, authority, and control over data assets throughout their lifecycle.	p39, p40, p48 p53, p54, p55, GL6, GL15, GL16, GL24.
AI and Advanced Technology Risks	Security challenges from emerging technologies.	P11, p17, p27, p29, P35, p43, p85, GL4, GL8, GL14, GL16, GL18, GL19, GL24, GL28

Organizational & Human Factors

Challenge Group	Description	Source Papers
Workforce and Skills Shortage	Critical gaps in cybersecurity expertise and available talent.	p56, p80, GL1, GL2, GL3, GL5, GL11, GL10, GL12, GL15, GL16, GL17, GL22
Human Error and Awareness	Security risks stemming from user behavior and awareness gaps	P2, P28, p36, p42, p44, p48, P57, P67, p76, GL3, GL12

Governance and Responsibility	Unclear delineation of security roles and accountability.	GL2, GL11, GL13, GL14, GL17, GL27
Economic & Regulatory Constraints		
Challenge Group	Description	Source Papers
Budget Limitations	Financial constraints affecting security implementation.	p65, p72, p76, P79, GL3, GL8, GL12, GL19, GL29
Regulatory and Compliance Complexity	Challenges navigating diverse regulatory requirements.	p39, GL1, GL5, GL11, GL16, GL21, GL25
Market and Development Pressures	Commercial dynamics affecting security priorities.	p58, p72, p80, GL7, GL12
Supply Chain Dependencies	Security risks originating from complex supplier ecosystems.	P57, GL3, GL12 GL14, GL16, GL18, GL21, GL20, GL29